

JURISPRUDENCE

DEVELOPMENT OF EU EMPLOYMENT DISCRIMINATION CASES

Nino Kutsniashvili

Lawyer,

PhD Candidate at Grigol Robakidze University, Tbilisi, Georgia

Supervisor: Valerian Khrustali

Abstract

This article examines the development of employment discrimination law within the European union, focusing in particular on the evolution of legal standards governing the burden of proof. Beginning with the inclusion of equal pay in the treaty of Rome, the EU has adopted a series of directives and ECJ rulings that progressively enhanced protection against discrimination. The article also touches on challenges in areas like religious discrimination and highlights the EU's broader commitment to workplace equality. The article analyzes the historical context, legislative milestones, and key case law shaping this development, while also considering the specific challenges of applying these principles in areas such as religious discrimination. By tracing the legal and procedural evolution of anti-discrimination norms in employment, this study highlights the EU's role in promoting fairness and equality in the workplace.

Keywords: Discrimination, the burden of proof, Religious Discrimination

Introduction

Employment discrimination law within the European union developed later than in jurisdictions such as the United States, largely due to the EU's nature as a supranational body and the gradual transfer of competences from its member states. Initially, before the treaty of Rome came into force in 1957, employment relationships were regulated solely by national laws and with the exception of France, most of the original member states lacked significant legislation on employment discrimination. This provision, originally aimed at ensuring fair economic competition, later became a foundation for border social objectives, as recognized by the European court of justice in its landmark *Defrenne II* decision. Since then, the EU has enacted some of the world's the most comprehensive anti-discrimination legislation, including directives addressing equal pay, equal treatment, pregnancy, parental leave and protections against discrimination based on race, religion, age and sexual orientation.

This article examines the development of EU discrimination law, with a particular focus on the evolution and application of burden of proof rules across directives and case law.

This study employs a doctrinal legal research methodology, which involved detailed examination and analysis of legal texts, including treaties, EU directives, case law of the court. It includes also comparative method, which is starting point in this article.

I. Historical Development of Employment Discrimination Law in the European Union

Given the relatively new vintage of the EC/EU and the fact that EU law is a product of the transferring of competence from Member States to a supranational body, it is not surprising that employment discrimination law initially developed somewhat later

and more slowly than in the United States. There, acting in the area of employment discrimination does not depend on a transfer of competence in any way. Nevertheless, even though significant similar antidiscrimination legislation in the field of employment law took longer to develop, today the EU has in place some of the most comprehensive antidiscrimination legislation in the world. Prior to the Treaty of Rome coming into force in 1957, national legislation governed the employer-employee relationship in each Member State. However, with the notable exception of France, most of the Member States of the then newly formed EEC did not have much on the books in the way of employment discrimination laws. French law, in contrast, provided for the equality of pay between men and women, a basic right that the other Member States belonging to the six original members of the EEC, did not legally recognize. In order to ease the concerns of the French that French industry employing a largely female workforce would suffer a competitive disadvantage as a result of industry in other Member States employing women at significantly lower wage rates, the Six included ex Article 119 EC (now Article 141 EC) on equal pay between men and women in the Treaty of Rome.¹ Only later did the European Court of Justice (ECJ) articulate the "social objective" of including this provision in the landmark decision known as *Defrenne II*. Both of these dual aims of pursuing social policy, that is, pursuing social measures for the sake of economic integration and in order to achieve "social progress," continue to be important objectives of the EU in making social policy. In addition to this antidiscrimination provision, the EEC Treaty also prohibited discrimination on the ground of nationality. The EEC Member States included this provision in order to facilitate free trade

¹ Haskovec J, "A Beast of a Burden - The New EU Burden-of-Proof Arrangement in Cases of Employment Discrimination Compared to Existing U.S. Law," *Transnational Law & Contemporary Problems* 14, no. 3 (Spring 2005): 1069-1106

and the growth of a common market in an area comprised of people of a variety of nationalities. Subsequently, the legislative organs of the EEC (and later, of the EC) enacted secondary law, consisting of several antidiscrimination directives. Among the first and most generally applicable of these directives are Directive 75/117/EEC², concerning equal pay between men and women, and Directive 76/207/EEC³, concerning equal treatment between men and women. At about this same time, the ECJ announced the existence of "a general principle of equality" in EC (then EEC) law. Litigants have relied upon the principle of equality in subsequent cases. Over the next several years, the legislative organs passed further directives in the area of equal pay and equal treatment in order to implement these principles more effectively. This secondary legislation included: Directives 86/613/EEC⁴, concerning equal treatment between men and women in various contexts; 92/85/EEC⁵, concerning pregnancy and maternity leave, *inter alia*; and 96/34/EC⁶, concerning parental leave.

II. Burden of proof in EU employment discrimination cases

The burden-of-proof in EU employment discrimination cases is set out in a series of three directives constituting a part of the EU antidiscrimination package of directives. As under U.S. law, the burden-of-proof arrangement in the EU similarly involves a shift in the burden-of-proof. The EU directives cover most aspects of the employment arrangement, either by expressly mentioning to which aspects they apply or by incorporating other EC law relating to employment by reference. Directive 97/80 applies to all "situations covered by Article 119 of the Treaty [involving equality of pay between men and women, now replaced by 136-143 EC and by Directives 75/117/EEC,⁷ 76/207/EEC,⁸ and, insofar as discrimination based on sex is concerned, 92/85/EEC and 96/34/EC.⁹

For the most part, these directives include a uniform clause allocating the burden-of-proof in employment discrimination cases. This clause states as

follows: Member States shall take measures as are necessary, in accordance with their national judicial systems, to ensure that, when persons who consider themselves wronged because the principle of equal treatment has not been applied to them establish, before a court or other competent authority, facts from which it may be presumed that there has been direct or indirect discrimination, it shall be for the respondent to prove that there has been no breach of the principle of equal treatment.¹⁰

III. Religious Discrimination

The employer has the responsibility of providing justification, with regard to the concrete tasks to be performed by each employee, demonstrating that its decision is proportionate and necessary and founded on objective elements unrelated to any form of discrimination."¹¹ Private businesses providing public services may do well to incorporate a religious neutrality requirement into their internal regulations: although not yet a legal obligation, proposed laws also supported an expansion of this obligation.¹² In its assessment of the limitation of freedoms in the *Baby Loup* case, the Conseil des Prud'hommes applied this type of "soft" norm the principle of secularism articulated in the day care center's staff rules to justify the nondiscriminatory character of the ban on the Islamic head covering. At first sight, this is a surprising decision, since the principle of religious neutrality does not generally apply to the private sector, despite the desire of some to see this happen. Upon further reflection, however, it is logical for the defense against an employee claiming a freedom to be positioned on a constitutional level, claiming the principle of secularism.¹³ Even in the workplace, where the opposite presumption is made, in the sense that the employee's subordination is the rule, an employee has a certain irreducible The Multiple Grounds of Discrimination autonomy and freedom that cannot be infringed upon by the employer."¹⁴ The growing visibility of an employee's religion reflects a change in paradigm for labor law from the "rights of

² Council Directive 75/117/EEC, 1975 O.J. (L 45/19) (on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to the application of the principle of equal pay for men and women) [hereinafter Directive 75/117/EEC].

³ Council Directive 76/207/EEC, 1976 O.J. (L 39/40) (on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion, and working conditions) [hereinafter Directive 76/207/EEC].

⁴ Council Directive 86/613/EEC, 1986 O.J. (L 359/56) (on the application of the principle of equal treatment between men and women engaged in an activity, including agriculture, in a self-employed capacity, and on the protection of self-employed women during pregnancy and motherhood).

⁵ Council Directive 92/85/EC, 1992 O.J. (L 348) (on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health at work of pregnant workers and workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding).

⁶ Council Directive 96/34/EC, 1996 O.J. (L 145/4) (concerning the framework agreement on parental leave concluded by UNICE (Employers' Confederations of Europe), CEEP (European Centre of Enterprises with Public Participation and of

Enterprises of General Economic Interest), and the ETUC (European Trade Union Confederation).

⁷ Directive 75/117/EEC, *supra* note 57.

⁸ Directive 76/207/EEC, *supra* note 58.

⁹ Directive 97/80/EC, *supra* note 76, art. 3.

¹⁰ Directive 97/80/EC, *supra* note 76, art. 4(1); Directive 2000/43/EC, *supra* note 75, art. 8(1); Directive 2000/78/EC, *supra* note 75, art. 10(1) (emphasis added).

¹¹ Mercat-Bruns, M. "Discrimination at work" - Comparing European, French, and American Law, University of California Press Oakland, California 2016 by The Regents of the University of California. Pg. 227-228.

¹² Gaudu, F. "L'entreprise de tendance laïque", 12 Dr. Soc. 1186, 1188 (2011), and the amended bill in the French Senate of Oct. 25, 2011, No. 56, and Report by High Council on Integration, opinion given on Sept. 1, 2011.

¹³ Mercat-Bruns, M. "Discrimination at work" - Comparing European, French, and American Law, University of California Press Oakland, California 2016 by The Regents of the University of California. Pg. 229.

¹⁴ Frouin, J-Y, "La protection des droits de la personne et des libertés du salarié", 99 Cah. Soc. du Barreau de Paris 123 (1998).

workers” to the “rights of people at work.”¹⁵ In France, there is an implicit agreement to respect the employee’s religion as long as it remains confined to the private sphere, as explained by the head advisor at the Cour de Cassation, Philippe Waquet, who promotes “a positive secularism that respects religious beliefs but confines them to the employee’s personal life.”¹⁶

Conclusion

The evolution of the burden of proof in employment discrimination cases in the EU reflects a significant shift towards strengthening the enforcement of the principles of equal treatment, particularly in matters of sex discrimination. The introduction and subsequent adoption of Directive 97/80/EC and related legislative measures formalised the shift of the burden of proof to employers once a claimant has established a *prima facie* case of discrimination. This procedural innovation contributes to wider access to justice for victims of discrimination by alleviating the evidentiary challenges faced by claimants. Furthermore, the case-law of the European Court of Justice has played a crucial role in shaping these legal standards, ensuring that indirect discrimination and opaque practices, such as opaque pay systems, are effectively addressed. The directives have helped to harmonise anti-discrimination protection across Member States, contributing to a more uniform application of equality rights in the field of employment.

Overall, the ongoing development of EU anti-discrimination law, including the burden of proof rules, marks progress towards enhanced protection against discrimination in the workplace. However, it also highlights the need for continued vigilance to ensure that legal frameworks remain effective and adaptable to the diverse social and cultural contexts in the Union.

References

1. Frouin, J-Y, “La protection des droits de la personne et des libertés du salarié”, 99 Cah. Soc. du Barreau de Paris 123 (1998).
2. Gaudu, F. “L’entreprise de tendance laïque”, 12 Dr. Soc. 1186, 1188 (2011), and the amended bill in the French Senate of Oct. 25, 2011, No. 56, and Report by High Council on Integration, opinion given on Sept. 1, 2011.

3. Haskovec J, "A Beast of a Burden - The New EU Burden-of-Proof Arrangement in Cases of Employment Discrimination Compared to Existing U.S. Law," *Transnational Law & Contemporary Problems* 14, no. 3 (Spring 2005): 1069-1106

4. Luxton L, "Equality and Sex Discrimination in the European Union - Is Shifting the Burden of Proof the Answer," *Dickinson Journal of International Law* 17, no. 2 (Winter 1999): pg. 375.

5. Mercat-Bruns, M. “Discrimination at work” - Comparing European, French, and American Law, University of California Press Oakland, California 2016 by The Regents of the University of California. Pg. 227-228.

6. Prechal, S. Burri, S. “EU Gender Equality Law”, Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, ISBN 978-92-79-10278-3 DOI 10.2767/62805, 2008. Pg. 19.

7. Ray. J-E, “D’un droit des travailleurs aux droits de la personne au travail”, 1 Dr. soc. 3 (2010).

8. Waquet, P. “La vie personnelle du salarié, in *Droit syndical et droits de l’homme à l’aube du XXIe siècle: mélanges en l’honneur de Jean-Maurice Verdier*” 181 (2001).

9. Council Directive 75/117/EEC, 1975 (on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to the application of the principle of equal pay for men and women).

10. Council Directive 76/207/EEC, 1976 O.J. (L 39/40) (on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion, and working conditions) [hereinafter Directive 76/207/EEC].

11. Council Directive 96/34/EC, 1996, (L 145/4) (concerning the framework agreement on parental leave concluded by UNICE (Employers' Confederations of Europe), CEEP (European Centre of Enterprises with Public Participation and of Enterprises of General Economic Interest), and the ETUC (European Trade Union Confederation)

12. Council Directive 75/117/EEC

13. Council Directive 97/80/EC

14. Council Directive 2000/43/EC

15. Council Directive 2000/78/EC

¹⁵ Ray. J-E, “D’un droit des travailleurs aux droits de la personne au travail”, 1 Dr. soc. 3 (2010).

¹⁶ Waquet, P. “La vie personnelle du salarié, in *Droit syndical et droits de l’homme à l’aube du XXIe siècle: mélanges en l’honneur de Jean-Maurice Verdier*” 181 (2001).